

CHROMOSOMAL POLYMORPHISM OF *BELGICA ANTARCTICA* JACOBS, 1900 (DIPTERA, CHIRONOMIDAE): REVEALED PATTERNS

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The Antarctic Peninsula region is currently one of the areas experiencing the most significant climate changes. Therefore, studying the adaptations of native biota to these changes and identifying potential relationships between chromosome polymorphism and specific environmental factors is essential for advancing scientific knowledge and developing strategies for biodiversity conservation. Chromosomal inversion polymorphism plays a crucial role in the adaptation of living organisms, particularly insects. Chromosomal polymorphism can be adaptive under certain conditions and is thought to be maintained by selective gradients. It is well established that chironomid *Belgica antarctica* Jacobs, 1900, an endemic species of the Antarctic Peninsula region, possesses polytene chromosomes in the salivary glands of its larvae. In salivary glands of all *B. antarctica* localities, the diploid chromosome set is $2n = 6$, with chromosomes I, II, and III. We found two types of inversions: inherited and somatic. Inherited heterozygous inversions have been identified in all chromosomes of this species. However, the relationship between the occurrence of specific inversions and environmental factors remains unexplored.

A total of 165 fourth-instar larvae, collected during the austral summer of 2022 from six different localities along the western part of the Antarctic Peninsula region, were analyzed. All five previously documented inherited heterozygous inversions from the XX century were detected and localized onto the chromosomes. Additionally, two novel heterozygous inversions were identified: inversion D1 (chromosome III, sections 2–10; frequencies from 20 to 51.61% depending on population), present in 56 individuals (33.94%) across all six localities, and a rare inversion in sections 9–11 of chromosome II (frequency 0.61%), found in a single individual at one sampling site (Roztochchia Ridge, Galindez Island, Argentine Islands). Numerous somatic aberrations and functional alterations were also observed across all three chromosomes, including heterozygous inversions, dark bands, heterozygous dark bands, trisomies, deficiencies, unpaired homologs, and an unexpressed nucleolar organizer region. It is known that the somatic functional and structural alterations in Chironomidae species are particularly suitable as biomarkers – they can be easily identified and used for detecting toxic agents in the environment.

An analysis of our data and all previous data from over 60 years presented in the literature on the frequencies of inherited heterozygous chromosomal inversions (a total of 1,436 *B. antarctica* specimens, 1,011 of which – or 70.4% – had at least one non-sex-linked inversion from 26 localities) was carried out to identify potential factors influencing their occurrence. We aimed to establish the potential differences in their frequencies depending on the locality, year of material collection, ecological complexity (related to substrate conditions), ornithogenic influence, and whether the substrate originated from nesting material. The results revealed that all inherited inversions, except for the rare inversion in sections 9–11 of chromosome II, showed variation among populations. However, most inversions were not influenced by the selected environmental factors. The only exception was inversion D1 on chromosome III, which was associated with ecological complexity (it was found in specimens collected from living mosses or bird nesting material, but not detritus or damp soil without

green vegetation) and collection year: notably, this inversion was detected in all localities sampled in 2022, whereas it was undocumented in earlier collections.

Furthermore, geographic trends were identified in the frequency of specific chromosomal inversions. Inversion A on chromosome II and inversion C on chromosome III were more prevalent in northern *B. antarctica* populations. In contrast, the inversion in sections 10–23 of chromosome I and inversion D1 on chromosome III were more common in southern populations. Additionally, longitude influenced the frequency of individuals carrying at least one inherited heterozygous inversion (excluding sex-linked inversion D on chromosome III): western localities (relative to the Antarctic Peninsula) exhibited a higher frequency of heterozygotes. Thus, the highest frequency (92%) was observed in the population from Pickwick Island, Pitt Islands – the westernmost locality – whereas the lowest frequency (16.05%) was recorded in the population near González Videla Base, one of the easternmost localities.

Overall, our findings indicate that chromosomal polymorphism in *B. antarctica* plays a significant role in its adaptation. However, the specific environmental factors driving the majority of these inversions remain undetermined.